

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE DIGITIZATION SYSTEM IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of digital technologies in modern higher education plays an important role in further strengthening the dynamics of the traditional form of education and creative processes. Accordingly, on a global scale, it is advisable to study experiments on this issue on a mutually beneficial basis.

All over the world, there is a sharp increase in computerization in production. The introduction of computer technology increases labor efficiency and productivity [1].

New generations of innovative technologies are penetrating into every aspect of production, which, of course, encourages a continuous increase in the skills of a specialist. In this regard, it is worth saying that as a result, the ability to manage, store, edit many databases increases significantly.

At the same time, computer technology is a factor in the formation and development of professional qualities of specialists. Computer technology has long been the most relevant tool in the educational process of teaching students. At the same time, students need to work with high-performance technologies, know how to use various 3D programs [2].

In addition to compulsory subjects, Informational Technologies are actively implemented in the field of education during the current digitization period.

This article is a study and analysis of world trends in the use of digitization technologies in higher education, as well as the application of higher education experiences abroad in this area in domestic higher education.

Innovative technologies and online platforms are being introduced into higher education all over the world, the relevance of the research is explained by the rapid transition of Higher Education of Uzbekistan to the ranks of this process.

In recent years, there have been serious and necessary changes in higher education, that is, developments in a new format are being mastered. A feature of these innovations is that, as a result of their increasing and frequent penetration, each innovation is an impetus to increase the level of education by developing educational directions.

Naturally, in order not to lag behind world educational standards and to implement new innovative technological developments in our local higher education institutions, it is

difficult to keep an eye on and analyze the world education system. The fact that many scientific articles are published in this area indicates that local higher education institutions are active in this issue.

In this, one can take an example from world experiments, for example, Russian scientists L.M.General principles of informatization of education were formulated by andryukhina and co-authors, pedagogical conditions for the use of it in this area were determined; didactic and technological principles of the formation and functioning of e-learning systems were developed.

Figure 1. Moodle virtual education tool example

In particular, the Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) virtual educational tool [Figure 1] is common in a number of Russian state institutions of higher education, such as Kazan, Tomsk, Vladivostok [3].

Figure 2. Moodle virtual education tool example

The experience of Kazan National Research Technological University shows that the Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) virtual learning tool (Figure 2) meets the requirements of traditional educational standards. It provides opportunities for students not only to get acquainted with theoretical materials and reporting work, but also to search and find information and information related to Science, Place creative projects or repeat reading the topics covered. This brings great interest in Informational Technologies in students and motivates them to innovational professional processes. It is at the Department of foreign languages of this higher educational institution that it is from this system that online learning of a foreign language, online testing, the performance of individual graduation projects is carried out.

Digitization increases the stimulus for the introduction of international educational platforms in higher education such as Coursera, edX, XuetangX, Udacity. Extensive research on the use of digital technology in universities in Europe, Australia and New Zealand, conducted by Jisc in 2017-2018 and covering a total of more than 83 students from 50,000 universities, revealed some of the most promising global trends in the field [4]. Research shows that the use of digital technologies has increased the ability to effectively apply and apply the education and knowledge gained to the life process

References:

1. Djuraeva Sh.G., Tashpulatov S.Sh., Cherunova I.V. Application of 3D technologies in modeling fashion design with elements of national decor. Bulletin of the Almaty Technological University. 2021;(3):60-67.
2. Tashpulatov, S.Sh., Djurayeva, Sh.G., & Murodov, T.B. (2018). Development of information support for decorative elements for fashion industry objects. International

Journal of European science review, ISSN 310-5577, Vienna, Austria, 7-8 , July-August, pp.225-228.

3. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tsifrovizatsiya-vysshego-obrazovaniya-novye-trendy-i-opyt-vnedreniya/viewer>

4. Romanova G. V. Preparing graduates for innovative engineering activities as the main task of a modern technical university // Management of sustainable development. – 2016. – № 4 (05). – C. 105–110
Jurayeva, S. G. (2021). 3D technologies in the process of designing a costume with traditional Uzbek decorative elements. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 08 (100), 7-11.<https://bugun.uz/2021/05/21/>

5. The law "On Official statistics" of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 11, 2021. // www.lex.uz

6. Djuraeva, Sh. G. Decorative ornaments used in modern costume / Sh. G. Djuraeva, S. Sh. Tashpulatov // Innovative technologies in textile and light industry : materials of reports of the international scientific and technical conference, November 26-27, 2014 / UO "VSTU". - Vitebsk, 2014. - pp. 142-143.

